

How are normative views and expectations related to social trust? An empirical test of moralistic and rationalistic theory

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Abstract

Social trust, the belief that others are trustworthy, has many societal benefits such as social cohesion and cooperation. While some theories argue that it arises from perceived shared moral values (moralistic perspective), others suggest it is based on rational expectations that others act in one's interest (rationalistic perspective). We are, according to our knowledge, the first to investigate which theory better describes the relationship between norm-related beliefs and social trust. We use regression and path analysis on survey data from 1,977 respondents, collected between June 2021 and February 2022, to analyse how respondents' beliefs about Covid-19 distancing norms affected their social trust. Our results support moralistic theory: perceiving others as having similar normative beliefs regarding norms increases social trust, whereas merely perceiving others as supportive of distancing norms does not. Additionally, we find that perceiving others as behaving differently from one's own normative beliefs decreases social trust partly because it shapes one's beliefs about others' normative beliefs. However, the perception of others' different behaviour also reduces trust independently of whether it is translated into others' different beliefs, suggesting an additional mechanism beyond existing theories.

1 Introduction

Social trust describes an individual's perception of others' trustworthiness (Uslaner, 2018). However, there is no general agreement on what this perception is built on (Nannestad, 2008). Some accounts treat social trust as a consequence of the perception that others share the same fundamental moral values (Uslaner, 2002, 2018). Others equate social trust with a person's rational evaluation of whether others will behave in line with their interests (Coleman, 1990; Hardin, 2002). Despite their differences, these accounts agree on the premise that *a person's trust in others is a cognitive state that depends on the person's perception of the cognitive states of others*. A person's perception that most other people are trustworthy (and thus can be trusted) could be tightly connected to that person's perception that most other people, respectively, share their moral values or are well-disposed. However, research relating people's social trust and their second order beliefs, i.e. beliefs about what others value, think and do, is rare. In this paper, we put forward and empirically test the argument that perceived compliance with social norms constitutes a fundamental channel through which a person's second order beliefs about others and trust in them are connected.

According to (Coleman, 1990) social norms are collective, endogenously shaped, macrolevel constructs that prescribe individual behaviour. Because social norms prescribe what each individual member of a group or society ought to do, they are likely the basis of one's beliefs about what unknown others might value and how they might act. Consequentially, a person's perception of what normative behaviours should be followed and what normative behaviours other members of society support and follow, will influence their social trust. To study the relation between norm-related beliefs and social trust, we follow other studies in the field and use Bicchieri's framework (Bicchieri & Xiao, 2009; Bicchieri, 2017) which distinguishes between three types of norm-related beliefs:

- 1) one's expectations that others support a norm-prescribed behaviour R (i.e. normative expectations – NE)
- 2) one's expectation that others behave according to a norm-prescribed behaviour R (i.e. empirical expectations – EE)

3) one's own support for a norm-prescribed behaviour R (personal normative beliefs – PNB)

According to this framework, a social norm exists when people support behaviour R (PNB), believe that other people also support R (NE), and believe that these other people also engage in R (EE). In this paper, however, we consider that PNB and NE , respectively, signal personal agreement and perceived agreement of others with a social norm (in this case distancing norms during the Covid-19 pandemic), whereas EE signal perceived compliance of others with the social norm.

Recent empirical findings suggest that these norm-related beliefs may relate to social trust in different ways. Lo Iacono et al. (2021) studied the changes in social trust in a representative sample of the Dutch population during the Covid-19 pandemic and found that, on average, respondents experienced a loss of social trust after the first wave of the pandemic. However, respondents who believed that most others support self-isolation norms (NE) and comply with self-isolation norms (EE), experienced a significantly smaller loss in social trust, if at all. Similarly, Wit and Lisciandra (2021), using 1999-2001 European Value Survey data, found that the more people follow civic norms in the respondent's eyes (EE), the higher is the respondent's social trust. These findings suggest that one's beliefs that most others support and adhere to norms that are set to benefit society are positively related to one's social trust. However, evidence regarding the relation of PNB and social trust is mixed. While respondents' beliefs that self-isolation norms should be followed were found to be negatively related with these respondents' social trust change in Lo Iacono et al. (2021), respondents' PNB regarding the legitimacy of civic norms was unrelated with these respondents' social trust in Wit and Lisciandra (2021).¹

These findings offer a first peek into the mechanisms that relate social norms to social trust (for a more comprehensive review, see Composto et al., 2025). However, it remains unclear how the interrelation of norm-related beliefs (i.e., NE , EE , and PNB) transforms the relationship between these norm-related beliefs and social trust. EE have been shown to influence one's NE (Horne et al., 2018; Horne & Przepiorka, 2021), which suggests that individuals assume others support the norms they

¹ Although Wit and Lisciandra (2021) refer to investigating the relation between NE and social trust, the measure of NE they find in European Value Survey ("Do you think behaviour R is justified") is conceptually closer to our measure of PNB . Hence, we interpret their findings regarding NE as findings regarding PNB .

seemingly follow. This implies that the relation of EE and social trust could be mediated by NE. Furthermore, Wit and Lisciandra (2021) found a significant correlation between respondents' PNB and EE, indicating that people project their own PNB onto their perception of other's normative behaviour, or, to reverse causal direction, that people's expectations about what others do fuel their own beliefs about what is right.

Our study aims to disentangle the relationship between social norms and trust by addressing how PNB, NE and EE are related with social trust. The contribution of our research is two-fold. First, by investigating the relationship of norm-related beliefs and social trust, we juxtapose two theories of social trust—i.e., social trust originating from moral values or from rational expectations—which both promise to shine a specific light on this very relationship. Secondly, we theoretically propose and empirically test a mediation mechanism through which norm-related beliefs and social trust are related.

We use survey data gathered in Italy during the Covid-19 pandemic to investigate how beliefs regarding distancing norms and social trust are related. In total, 1977 respondents participated in the Covid Risk Survey that was conducted in ten consecutive waves between June 2021 and February 2022. The survey measures respondents' PNB, NE and EE for ten different behaviours prescribed by Covid-19 distancing norms. Social trust was elicited by means of an 11-point social trust item. We first perform principal component analyses to examine whether measures of PNB, NE and EE capture different norm dimensions; roughly half of the items refer to norms that apply in the private domain and the other half norms that apply in the public domain. We then use regression and path analysis to test predictions about the relationship between social norms and trust stemming from the moral-value and rational-expectations perspectives on social trust. However, the embeddedness of our study in the (Italian) Covid-19 context has advantages and disadvantages that are important to mention upfront.

During the pandemic, Covid-19 related measures were brought to the forefront of political, moral, and social debates, which transformed the topic of Covid-19 into a highly polarizing one (Bobba & Hubé, 2021; Hart et al., 2020). Because of these debates, people's social trust could have been influenced more profoundly by their perceptions of other people's stances on Covid-19 measures compared to norms unrelated to the pandemic. Studying the relation between social norms and trust in

a non-pandemic situation would require to first correctly identify which social norms people care and are knowledgeable about. What is more, Covid-19 measures required a great deal of sacrifice in terms of individuals' freedoms and lifestyles. The increased "burden" that pandemic norms brought about might have changed how people's social trust was affected by perceived norm violations. On the one hand, because the individual burden of complying with distancing norms was high, people might have been more forgiving of norm deviations and their trust less affected by non-compliance (Horne & Johnson, 2021). On the other hand, because norm violations contributed to the spread of an unknown disease, collective risks associated with norm violations might have been perceived as exceptionally high, which could have made people less forgiving of norm violations (Horne & Johnson, 2021) and their trust more affected by non-compliance (Lo Iacono et al., 2021). To conclude, the pandemic created a "magnifying glass" that facilitated the studying of the relation between social norms and social trust (for a related account of how the pandemic affected social trust in Italy, see Gambetta & Morisi, 2022). However, the specificity of the pandemic context to some extent limits the generalizability of our findings to other norms and contexts.

2 Theoretical background

2.1 Two tales about social trust

One way to juxtapose competing theories of social trust is that social trust is perceived as either rooted in shared fundamental moral values with other people or in a rational perception of other people's trustworthiness (Frederiksen, 2019; Hardin, 2002; Nannestad, 2008; Uslaner, 2018). Treating norm-related beliefs as determinants of social trust enables us to compare the two theories of trust since they both assume that social trust depends on individual beliefs about others – and these beliefs are influenced by social norms.

According to the moralistic perspective on social trust, social trust is founded upon shared fundamental moral values (Uslaner, 2002). Most people will perceive their moral values to be aligned with trustworthiness and good intentions. In other words, having any moral values will be accompanied by a belief that one's moral values are in fact "the right" values, indicative of trustworthiness, and

should be valued by everyone. However, the content of fundamental moral values can differ from person to person. Yet, regardless of a person's assumed moral values, they will be more likely to trust another person if they believe the other person shares their moral values which they perceive as indicative of trustworthiness. Hence, *according to the moralistic theory of trust, social trust develops when a person perceives that many other people in society share their fundamental moral values*. If a person perceives to be surrounded by "their" moral community (Uslaner, 2002), i.e., if the number of those with similar values is perceived to be large, they will perceive most people as trustworthy and having good intentions.

There are some empirical findings supporting the moralistic perspective on social trust. Frederiksen (2019) combined survey measures of social trust and interviews with respondents and found that respondents with high social trust believe that most other people have similar moral values and would distrust people who would express fundamentally different values, for example, people with radical political beliefs that respondents morally oppose. Congruently, these respondents are, although expressing high levels of social trust, distrustful of value outsiders (Frederiksen, 2019), which indicates social trust might be grounded in perceptions of shared moral values.

The rationalistic perspective to social trust stresses that trust is rooted in a person's estimation of others' potential behaviour in relation to their personal interests (Hardin, 2002). Trust is founded upon a person's belief that others are unlikely to voluntarily behave in a way that is damaging to the person (Gambetta, 1988). For development of trust, it is not only important that others merely act in line with another's interest but that this act is a consequence of their choice rather than coercion (Gambetta, 1988). *According to rationalistic theory of trust, social trust emerges when a person perceives that many other members of society have a preference to not harm other members of society (and even further others' interests) (Delhey & Newton, 2005)*. In other words, to have social trust is to believe that the probability of other members of society voluntarily acting against another person's interest is relatively low (Coleman, 1990).

Frederiksen (2019) also found that (a subset of) people do perceive social trust in rationalistic terms. Some respondents believed that members of society are motivated by their own interests but still

prefer to pursue personal gain through cooperation with (rather than harming) others, which made them trustworthy in respondents' eyes. Figure 1 summarizes the two perspectives on social trust schematically.

FIGURE 1. Moralistic and rationalistic theories of social trust

2.2 *Who is trustworthy and why?*

How can norm-related beliefs further our understanding of mechanisms of social trust, be they grounded in the perceived sharing of fundamental moral values with others or the perceived presence of other-regarding preferences in others? Since norms are macrolevel constructs that prescribe behaviour at the individual level (Coleman, 1990), people should infer what other members of society value and do based on norms they expect these others to follow and support (Falcone et al., 2013).

The present study measures normative expectations (NE), empirical expectations (EE) and personal normative beliefs (PNB) regarding norms that prescribed different social distancing behaviours to prevent the spread of Covid-19. How do they translate into the moralistic or rationalistic perspective on social trust?²

² Corresponding to each perspective on social trust, we make two interpretations of the distancing norms we measured. First, within the moralistic perspective, distancing norms are interpreted as indicative of one's moral

According to the moralistic perspective, a person's social trust depends on their perception of how many others share their moral values. Therefore, during the pandemic, a person's social trust would increase if they perceived that many other people supported the social distancing norms, they themselves supported. This is because a person perceiving others (dis)approve of the same norms they (dis)approve of, infer that these others share similar values, which indicates their trustworthiness. For example, a person who believes it is appropriate to hug friends and family during Covid-19 pandemic will have higher social trust if they believe many other people believe this is appropriate too. This is because they perceive their own choice of rejecting the norm as morally "correct" and will assign trustworthiness to those who also "correctly" chose the same attitude. Correspondingly, if a person perceives many others disagree with their belief that one can have physical contact with close friends and family, they will less likely perceive these others as trustworthy. Therefore, we hypothesize that: *the bigger the difference between a person's PNB and the person's NE, the lower will be the person's social trust (H1a).*

According to the rationalistic perspective, a person's social trust depends on them perceiving many others to have other-regarding preferences. Therefore, as distancing norms promoted behaviours that would protect others from being harmed, people who supported these norms could have been seen as having other-regarding preferences. Consequently, if a person perceived many others supporting Covid-19 related distancing norms, their social trust should be higher. For example, even if a person thinks hugging close friends and relatives is appropriate and thus rejects the norm that suggests physical distancing from close relations, the person could still assume the stance that people who support the norm of physical distancing from friends and family care about other people's health. Hence, regardless of a person's PNB, the person's perception of others' support for distancing norms would increase the

values. This interpretation is supported by the fact that distancing norms generally suggested curtailing some individual freedoms (e.g., seeing friends and family, engaging in leisure activities, political participation) infringing values and rights embodied in those freedoms to prioritize values embodied in stopping the pandemic and protecting general health. Second, within the rationalistic perspective, distancing norms are interpreted as univocally promoting a collective good, namely preventing the spread of a disease that would negatively affect public health.

person's social trust. Correspondingly, we hypothesize that: *the lower a person's NE, the lower will be the person's social trust* (H1b).

2.3 From perceived behaviour to perceived beliefs

So far, we have related one's social trust to one's perceived beliefs of others. But how does one form a belief about what unknown members of society believe? A mechanism that individuals use to draw conclusions and predictions about other people's actions is *attribution* (Kelley, 1973). According to attribution theory (Kelley, 1973; Kelley & Michela, 1980), people tend to causally explain others' behaviour by attributing their behaviour to different causes including inner causes such as intentions, plans and beliefs. Attribution theory can thus be applied to argue that a person is likely to infer what norms other people support from what they observe or believe these other people do. For example, if a person believes other people follow the norm of physical distancing from close friends and family (EE), they are likely to attribute this behaviour to these other people's approval of the norm (NE) (Horne et al., 2018; Przepiorka et al., 2022). Correspondingly, if a person perceives others do not adhere to the norm of physical distancing from close friends and family, they will ascribe their disagreement with the norm as a cause of their nonconformist behaviour. Therefore, we hypothesize that: *the higher a person's EE, the higher will be the person's NE* (H2).

Combining the argumentations leading up to hypotheses H1a, H1b and H2, it follows that the relation between the perception of others' norm-related behaviours and social trust will be mediated by perceptions of other's normative beliefs. How a person's perception of others' normative beliefs works as such a mediator depends on whether trust is grounded in moralistic or rationalistic reasoning. In case of the moralistic perspective, we hypothesize that *the relation of social trust and the difference between PNB and EE will be fully mediated by the difference between PNB and NE* (H3a).

We use the difference between PNB and EE because perceived behaviour of others alone cannot be fully informative about a person's perceived difference between beliefs of others and their own beliefs. Whether a rise in perceived conformist behaviour of others leads to an increase or decrease of perceived difference in one's own and others' beliefs depends on one's own beliefs. In order to be in

line with the moralistic perspective and keep the perceived difference between one's own and other's beliefs as a mediator of the effect of perceived behaviour, perceived behaviour must include a reference to one's own beliefs. This makes theoretical sense: a person can directly "observe" their own beliefs and the behaviour of others, but they cannot directly observe others' beliefs. Therefore, if our mediation mechanism holds and perceptions of others' behaviour are translated into perceptions of others' beliefs, a person's perception that others behave differently than the person's values prescribe, should be translated into the person's perception that others have different values than they do. Furthermore, in case of the rationalistic perspective, we hypothesize that *the relation of social trust with EE will be fully mediated by NE (H3b)*. These hypotheses are illustrated in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2. Rationalistic and moralistic models extended with mediation of perceived behaviour

2.4 Differences between distancing norms

Distancing norms during the pandemic comprised several domains. Some distancing norms referred to behaviours in public places that are easily observable by others (like shaking hands, standing within one meter distance from other people or visiting public events), whereas some norms referred to behaviours in private spaces unlikely to be observed by unknown others (such as socializing with or hugging close friends or relatives). However, the public and private categories are not the only relevant categories in which we could divide distancing norms. People might also hold different norm-related beliefs conditional on the norm's prescription of social or physical distancing. For example, physical contact (kissing, hugging, or standing close to each other) might have been perceived as riskier compared to social contact (visiting public events or socializing with family and friends). Furthermore, some norms refer to leisure activities (such as attending personal events like parties or attending public events like concerts), whereas some norms refer to more practical behaviours one might not have a good alternative to (such as using public transport or visiting public places where many people gather).

To conclude, because distancing norms differ in various aspects (such as private/public, physical/social, and others) we will first examine if the different examples of distancing norms capture one or several domains of distancing, and, if that is the case, adapt our analysis. After all, if we would indeed find different domains, that could lead to distinct relationships between PNB, NE, and EE, and their effects on social trust. For instance, if we were to find the public/private distinction, it could be that supporting distancing in public settings might be interpreted as more indicative of other-regarding preferences compared to distancing in private spaces, as the first protects strangers while the latter protects loved ones. The positive effect of perceived conformism on social trust might then be greater for norms referring to public than private spaces. Since we have no a priori reasons to anticipate one division over another, any revelation of multiple domains of distancing norms, and consequently their effects on social trust, will be studied through exploratory analyses.

2.5. Causality

We proposed two causal theoretical models on how individuals' social trust will be affected by these individuals' perceptions of other people's support for social distancing norms that emerged as a result of the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic. However, note that our two models merely differ in the way the explanatory constructs are conceptualized; their causal structures, i.e. how the explanatory constructs are related to the outcome of interest, is the same in both models. The causal structure is justified by the sequence of events. First, the pandemic broke out. Second, distancing norms emerged or were introduced. Third, people could observe their fellow citizens' behaviour and form expectations about their adherence to distancing norms. Fourth, people could form expectations about their fellow citizen's support for distancing norms. Fifth, these normative expectations would affect people's trust in their fellow citizens (or generalized others).

It is conceivable that people's social trust may have affected how these people came to perceive their fellow citizens' support and adherence to distancing norms in the first place (Frederiksen, 2019). However, we deem the outbreak of the pandemic a too disruptive an event to make pre-pandemic social trust a relevant determinant of perceived support and adherence to distancing norms compared to the pandemic itself. The pandemic led to significant changes in social relations, the type of contexts in which people would encounter their fellow citizens, and the types of behaviours these fellow citizens would engage in in these contexts. In other words, even though pre-pandemic social trust might have affected perceived support and adherence to distancing norms, the pandemic provided people with ample opportunities (and reasons) to estimate others' distancing beyond their pre-pandemic social trust and revise their beliefs about the trustworthiness of their fellow citizens.

Yet, not everyone was affected in the same way by the pandemic in terms of the changes in the social structure. It is therefore important to consider the factors that have likely affected both, people's perceptions of their fellow citizens' support or adherence to distancing norms and these people's trust in their fellow citizens. These factors constitute potential confounders of the causal relations postulated in our theoretical models and therefore need to be included as control variables in our statistical models (Kohler et al., 2024). We describe the rationale for the control variables we selected as well as their operationalizations in the next section.

3 Data and Methods

3.1 Data collection and survey design

This study uses a cross-sectional data gathered by The Institute of Cognitive Sciences and Technologies of the Italian National Research Council. The study collected survey data from June 2021 to February 2022 among a sample of residents of Rome. The survey was administered through Qualtrics with respondents from the Qualtrics panel. The data was collected in 10 waves, every two weeks from to August 2021 and every month from October 2021 until February 2022 (online appendix Section 1). Altogether, 1977 respondents were surveyed. Each wave was stratified on gender and age such that the two genders would be represented equally, and age would be evenly distributed across three categories (less than 30, between 30 and 50 and above 50 years old) in the sample. At the time of the survey, all respondents lived in Rome, Italy, such that the expectations we asked about were all about the same reference population. Since we do not investigate time trends, we treat all respondents as a part of one sample and control for the wave respondents belonged to (see below for details of selected control variables).

The survey first presented all respondents with Covid-19 statistics on infection, mortality, and vaccination rates for the two preceding weeks to minimize differences in respondents' knowledge about the latest Covid-19 developments. Then it gathered information about respondent's objective risk factors regarding Covid-19 and their risk perceptions related to economic and social consequences of the pandemic. Furthermore, respondents' social trust as well as trust in political and medical institutions was measured. The central part of the survey measured respondents' perceptions of different Covid-19-related norms and how the norms are, in respondents' opinions, perceived and adhered to by other people. These other people were referred to as the citizens of Rome participating in the survey. This was done so to minimize differences in the interpretation of norms and norm compliance among respondents. In each wave respondents' answers to questions regarding EE and NE were incentivized. In each wave, the respondent whose combined answers to the EE and NE of all distance norms most

closely matched, respectively, the modal reported behaviour and PNB for the corresponding norms was rewarded with a bonus of €25.

3.2. Variables

Outcome variable

Social trust was measured with the question “On a scale from zero to ten, where zero is not at all and ten is completely, in general, how much do you trust most people?”. This is a variation of generalized trust question, also referred to as GTQ, that has been shown to be the more valid measure of generalized trust due to its neutral and symmetrical formulation (OECD, 2017).

Explanatory variables

Respondents were asked about their and others’ perceptions regarding 10 different Covid-19-related norms. Respondent’s personal normative beliefs (PNB), empirical expectations (EE), and normative expectations (NE) were measured for the 10 behaviours prescribed by distancing norms listed below.

- 1) shaking hands with others
- 2) keeping at least 1m distance from other people outside of the home
- 3) attending personal events such as parties, weddings, funerals
- 4) getting together with friends and family
- 5) visit public places where many people gather
- 6) hugging close friends or relatives
- 7) going to restaurants
- 8) kissing close friends or relatives
- 9) taking public transport
- 10) attending public events such as concerts or festivals

Personal normative beliefs (PNB) about Covid-19-related norms were measured on a 6-point scale with the question “We now ask you to indicate for each of the following behaviours to what extent

you find them socially appropriate, considering that one means you find the behaviour extremely inappropriate while 6 means you find it extremely appropriate". Possible answers were (1) *Extremely inappropriate*, (2) *Rather inappropriate*, (3) *A little inappropriate*, (4) *A little appropriate*, (5) *Rather appropriate*, (6) *Extremely appropriate*.

Normative expectations (NE) were measured by asking respondents "According to you, what is the most frequent answer given by the people of Rome taking part in this survey to the question: "To what extent do you find the following behaviours socially appropriate?". The possible answers were the same as for measuring respondent's personal normative beliefs: (1) *Extremely inappropriate*, (2) *Rather inappropriate*, (3) *A little inappropriate*, (4) *A little appropriate*, (5) *Rather appropriate*, (6) *Extremely appropriate*.

Empirical expectations (EE) for each norm were measured by asking respondents to guess the most common answer to questions about following norms among other respondents. Specifically, respondents were asked: "According to you, what is the most frequent answer given by the people of Rome taking part in this survey to the question: "How often do you engage in the following behaviours?". Possible answers were: (1) *Never*, (2) *Rarely*, (3) *Sometimes*, (4) *Often*, (5) *Always*. The three sets of 10 variables containing PNB, NE and EE are treated as continuous.

Control variables

Wave in which the data was gathered is controlled for since perception of the health crisis was changing in relation to changes in the severity of Covid-19 risk and to new information regarding the virus outbreak. Covid-19 infection and mortality rates changed across the ten waves. Moreover, Italy experienced politicization of the pandemic and consequential conflict and polarization during Covid-19 progression (Charron et al., 2023; Russo & Valbruzzi, 2022). Timing could have affected people's social trust, perceived behaviour of others (EE) and perceived beliefs of others (NE), e.g. because of changes in infection rates and the importance of adhering to preventative measures (Vriens et al., 2024). Therefore, for each wave a dummy variable was created and included in the analysis.

Education has been shown to affect one's level of social trust in many cross-sectional studies investigating different contexts (Dinesen & Bekkers, 2017). Positive effect of education on trust (Knack & Keefer, 1997) was explained through mechanisms such as its contribution to a person's resources (Delhey & Newton, 2003), intelligence (Yamagishi, 2001) or adaptation of cosmopolitan values (Borgonovi, 2012). Furthermore, those with different education might refer to different networks regarding resources and values when they form their NE and EE. Consequently, education might affect what kind of normative beliefs and behaviours a person generalizes to "most others". Educational level of respondents was measured with a question "*What is your highest educational degree?*". Possible answers were: (1) *No degree/elementary school*, (2) *Middle school*, (3) *High school*, (4) *Bachelor*, (5) *Master* and (6) *PhD*. Based on the Italian educational system,³ respondents were assigned the number of years they spent in education institutions, namely 5, 8, 13, 16, 18 and 22 for the respective categories. Education was then included in the analysis as a continuous control variable.

Perception of risk of Covid-19 for economic resources is also controlled for as economic resources and threat of unemployment have been shown to affect social trust (Delhey & Newton, 2003; Dinesen & Bekkers, 2017). Furthermore, those under economic risk could have projected or compared their economic circumstances to others, affecting their assessment of how many other people are willing to follow (EE) and support (NE) social distancing. The perception of financial risk as a consequence of Covid-19 was measured by asking respondents "*Please indicate how much of a threat, if any, the coronavirus outbreak is to your personal financial safety?*". Possible answers were (1) "*Not a threat*", (2) "*A little threatening*", (3) "*Rather threatening*" and (4) "*A major threat*". The variable is treated as continuous.

Risk attitude is controlled for since risk attitudes have been shown to be connected to one's tendency to trust (Schechter, 2007). Furthermore, perception of risk could also affect NE and EE, as people are likely to infer other's beliefs and behaviour assuming others share their risk perceptions. Respondent's risk attitude was measured by asking "*On a scale of zero to ten, are you generally a*

³ <https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-education-systems/italy/overview>

person who is fully prepared to take risks (0) or do you try to avoid taking risks (10)?” The variable is treated as continuous.

Age was measured by asking respondents “*What is your age?*”. The answers were given in years. It will be treated as a continuous control variable as the trust item is sensitive to age (OECD, 2017) and age could have affected NE and EE, since reference networks are age-based and distancing behaviours could have differed between ages due to different health vulnerability.

Gender of a respondent was marked with a question “*What is your gender?*” with answers (1) “*Male*”, (2) “*Female*” and (3) “*Other*”. It is treated as a categorical control variable as trust item has been shown to be sensitive to gender (OECD, 2017), which could also be true for NE and EE since reference networks and attitude towards norms are gendered (Mayo, 2017).

3.3. Data preparation and methods

Data preparation

Variables measuring EE, NE, and PNB related to all norms except *keeping at least 1 meter distance from people outside of home* were reversed. As a result, higher values of PNB indicate higher support for distancing norms and higher values of NE and EE indicate, respectively, higher perceived support of and perceived adherence to distancing norms. Since there are only four participants with missing data, two participants who made a mistake reporting their age (reported age was less than 18), and five participants who did not identify as a man or a woman (which is too little to analyse them as a separate category), list wise deletion of these respondents was performed, leaving 1966 respondents for the analyses.

Modelling differences among norms

Distancing norms differ in aspects that might be relevant for the relationships between norm-related beliefs and social trust. Therefore, before modelling structural relationships between norm-related beliefs and social trust, we conducted principal component analysis (PCA) to examine how variance within PNB, NE, and EE is organized among the 10 items (descriptive statistics for all 30 items are

provided in the online appendix in Section 2). The analysis was done in R using the “psych” package. Based on the appropriate number of components extracted with PCA, norm items are summed into component scores and these score variables may be used to test hypotheses in subsequent analyses. When choosing the relevant number of components to represent variability of PNB, NE and EE, the present paper uses two criteria. First, components used in subsequent analysis must be theoretically justified – theoretically interpretable rather than representing a specific item and its relation to other items. Second, a component’s eigenvalue must be greater than one (Keiser rule) so that it contains at least as much variance as a single item.

Modelling of structural relationships between norm-related beliefs and social trust

We used regression analysis and structural equation modelling (SEM) to test our hypotheses. Violation of the multinomial normality assumption was remedied by choosing a robust maximum likelihood estimator for standard errors (Kline, 2016). Based on constructed variables representing scales of PNB, NE and EE, the complementary difference variables are calculated. The difference between a respondent’s PNB and NE and their PNB and EE are calculated as $|PNB-NE|$ and $|PNB-EE|$ and referred to as perceived belief opposition and perceived behaviour opposition, respectively. When calculating perceived behaviour opposition, the five-point scale of EE was transformed to match the six-point scale of PNB.

Hypothesis testing was performed in three stages. Models in stage one test hypotheses *H1a* and *H1b*. The *Moralistic model* predicts social trust based on perceived belief opposition $|PNB-NE|$, whereas the *Rationalistic model* predicts social trust based on NE (see Figure 2). We compare the two regression models based on explained variance and significance of estimated parameters. Furthermore, we test whether including the variable of perceived belief opposition or NE significantly improves the fit of the model compared to when the effect of each variable is not estimated but instead restricted to zero. Based on the fit of the models and relevant variables’ effects, we further test mediation hypotheses *H2* and *H3*. Within the *Moralistic model*, in which perceived belief opposition (and not NE) is affecting social trust, *H2* and *H3* are modelled using perceived behaviour opposition (and not EE). In stage two, the direct effect of EE (*Rationalistic model*) or perceived behaviour opposition (*Moralistic model*) on

social trust is established. In the third stage, we establish whether there is (full or partial) mediation of this effect (see Figure 2).

Models' goodness of fit is compared in terms of the model chi-square statistics, the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA), comparative fit index (CFI), and standardized root mean square residual (SRMR). The thresholds for good model fit set for the last three goodness of fit statistics follow common scientific practice and are $RMSEA < 0.05$, $CFI > 0.95$, $SRMR < 0.08$ (Kline, 2016). Specifically, the model chi-square tests whether the difference between model-generated predictions and actual data is significant, however, the chi-square statistic is expected to be higher (and so the model fit worse) for large sample sizes like ours (Kline, 2016, pp. 270–272). RMSEA is a continuous scale with lower values indicating less departures from approximate fit. It is based on the model's chi-square statistics but, unlike model chi-square test, it “punishes” models with less degrees of freedom (like ours). CFI measures model fit relative to the baseline model (in which covariances between endogenous variables are zero) indicating how much the researcher's model improves model fit relative to the baseline model where the value 0.95 means that the model's fit is about 95% better than the fit of the baseline model (Kline, 2016, pp. 276–277). CFI “punishes” models with greater complexity but is less sensitive to degrees of freedom. SRMR complements CFI by measuring the overall difference between observed and predicted correlations with higher values indicating that there might be model misspecifications. Unlike CFI which compares a model's fit in relation to the baseline model, SRMR compares predicted correlations to observed ones. We choose these four measures of fit because they represent a minimum set of indices that, by depending on different aspects of the model, wholesomely represent the global model fit (Kline, 2016).

4 Results

4.1. Principal component analysis (PCA) of norm-related beliefs

We first focused on establishing how many principal components should be extracted to explain the variability of items within PNB, NE and EE. We therefore conducted PCA based on the 10-item

correlation matrices of PNB, NE and EE separately. The three correlation matrices are provided in the online appendix in Section 3. Table 1 lists the Eigenvalues of the 10 components for PNB, NE and EE separately. Table 2 shows the component loadings on all 10 items for PNB, NE and EE separately.

Table 1: Eigenvalues of the 10 components for PNB, NE and EE

<i>Comp.</i>	<i>PNB</i>		<i>NE</i>		<i>EE</i>	
	<i>Eigen value</i>	<i>% explained variance</i>	<i>Eigen value</i>	<i>% explained variance</i>	<i>Eigen values</i>	<i>% explained variance</i>
1	5.08	0.51	5.31	0.53	5.15	0.52
2	1.21	0.12	1.22	0.12	1.03	0.10
3	0.87	0.09	0.72	0.07	0.79	0.08
4	0.59	0.06	0.59	0.06	0.64	0.06
5	0.53	0.05	0.50	0.05	0.55	0.05
6	0.46	0.05	0.41	0.04	0.50	0.05
7	0.44	0.04	0.39	0.04	0.42	0.04
8	0.35	0.04	0.34	0.03	0.39	0.04
9	0.29	0.03	0.29	0.03	0.31	0.03
10	0.18	0.02	0.22	0.02	0.22	0.02

According to the Kaiser rule and the numbers listed in Table 1, two components should be extracted. However, the results in Table 2 show that the first component has substantial loadings on all items but the “distance” item (2) across all three norm-related beliefs, whereas the second component mainly captures the distance item and its contrast to the “restaurant” and “getting together with friends and family” items. The reason for this could be that the distance item was formulated in a reversed way; unlike the other nine items, it asked participants about their acceptance of obeying rather than breaking a norm. This may have gone unnoticed by some respondents. Because we do not have good theoretical reasons to argue that the distance item alone captures a meaningful dimension of norm-related beliefs and the gain in explained variance from a second component would be modest anyways, we conduct all our subsequent analyses based on one component per norm-related belief extracted from nine items (excluding the distance item).

Table 2: Loadings of the first two principal components for PNB, NE and EE

<i>Item</i>	<i>PNB</i>			<i>NE</i>			<i>EE</i>		
	<i>Load. C1</i>	<i>Load. C2</i>	<i>Expl. var.</i>	<i>Load. C1</i>	<i>Load. C2</i>	<i>Expl. var.</i>	<i>Load. C1</i>	<i>Load. C2</i>	<i>Expl. var.</i>
1	0.73	0.29	0.62	0.73	0.29	0.61	0.67	0.24	0.51
2	0.30	0.81	0.75	0.17	0.87	0.78	0.29	0.86	0.82
3	0.78	-0.12	0.62	0.80	-0.11	0.65	0.78	-0.08	0.61
4	0.68	-0.40	0.62	0.73	-0.37	0.67	0.72	-0.34	0.64
5	0.81	-0.08	0.66	0.82	0.00	0.67	0.80	-0.11	0.66
6	0.81	0.06	0.67	0.81	0.08	0.67	0.81	0.01	0.65
7	0.64	-0.45	0.61	0.69	-0.39	0.63	0.75	-0.22	0.61
8	0.81	0.19	0.70	0.81	0.19	0.69	0.80	0.11	0.65
9	0.63	-0.13	0.42	0.70	-0.12	0.51	0.65	-0.11	0.43
10	0.78	0.17	0.63	0.80	0.18	0.67	0.76	0.16	0.60

Results of the PCA with nine items are, in terms of Eigen values and component loadings, very similar to the results of the PCA with ten items and are therefore only presented in the online appendix (Section 4). For all three norm-related beliefs, the first component satisfies the Keiser criteria and explains 56%, 59% and 56% percent of variance within PNB, NE and EE, respectively (online appendix Section 4).

Our PCA analysis shows that there are no relevant groupings among items. We therefore “merge” all nine items into a single score by using the average of items as predictors of social trust representing PNB, NE and EE. We could use component scores but since items load on one component and the correlation between principal component scores and averaged items scores for the nine items is above 0.998 for all three norm-related beliefs, we keep the solution that maintains the scale of original items.

Table 3 provides the descriptive statistics of the variables used in our subsequent analyses.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics for variables used in SEM analysis (except controls for wave)

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard deviation</i>	<i>Min.</i>	<i>Max.</i>	<i>N</i>
Dependent variable					
<i>Social trust</i>	5.3	2.1	1	10	1966
Constructed variables					
<i>PNB</i>	4.14	1.04	1	6	1966
<i>NE</i>	3.86	1.00	1	6	1966
<i>EE</i>	3.18	0.73	1	5	1966
<i>PNB-NE</i>	0.74	0.74	0	5	1966
<i>PNB-EE</i>	0.86	0.76	0	5	1966
Controls					
<i>Waves 1 – 10 (0/1)</i>	n/a	n/a	0	1	1966

<i>Education (in years)</i>	15.2	3.2	5	22	1966
<i>Age (in years)</i>	43.1	14.5			1966
<i>Female (0/1)</i>	0.51		0	1	1966
<i>Perceived economic threat</i>	2.7	0.90	1	4	1966
<i>Risk attitude</i>	5.4	2.4	1	10	1966

4.2. Structural equation modelling

Moralistic or Rationalistic model of trust

In the first stage we compare the *Moralistic* and *Rationalistic models* of social trust (Table 4) based on explained variance and parameter significance. Furthermore, we compare the *Moralistic* and *Rationalistic models* to their restricted versions in which the effects of, respectively, perceived belief opposition $|PNB-NE|$ and NE, are not estimated but instead restricted to zero. If the restricted model does not significantly differ in its predictions compared to the unrestricted model, the unrestricted model, despite its higher complexity, does not have more explanatory power. This would imply that the additional parameter is redundant.

In the *Moralistic model* social trust is predicted based on perceived belief opposition and controls. The effect of perceived belief opposition in the *Moralistic model* is significant and negative (Table 4), namely a 1 unit increase in perceived belief opposition (the direction of the difference does not matter), leads to a 0.33 unit decrease in social trust ($b = -0.330$, $p < 0.001$). In the extreme, this means that someone who perceives their own views to completely oppose those of others (i.e., who has a perceived belief opposition score of 5) is predicted to have 1.65 units less social trust than someone who perceives their own views to perfectly align with those of others. This model explains 17% of the variance in social trust ($R^2 = 0.170$; $R^2_{Adj.} = 0.164$; $F(15, 1950) = 25.44$, $p < 0.001$). Comparing the *Moralistic model* to its restricted version where the effect of perceived belief opposition is not estimated but restricted to zero (model presented in Section 7 in online appendix) shows that restricting the main effect of perceived behaviour opposition significantly worsens the model fit ($\Delta\chi^2(1) = 31.373$, $p < 0.001$), justifying the inclusion of the main effect of this variable in the model.

In the *Rationalistic model*, social trust is predicted by NE and controls (Table 4). This model explains less variance than the *Moralistic model* ($R^2 = 0.157$; $R^2_{Adj.} = 0.150$; $F(15, 1950) = 21.26$, $p <$

0.001) and the effect on NE is not significant ($b = 0.012, p = 0.80$). Comparing the *Rationalistic model* to its restricted version in which the effect of NE is not estimated but restricted to zero (Section 7 in online appendix) shows that restricting the main effect of NE does not significantly worsen the model fit ($\Delta\chi^2(1) = 0.076, p < 0.783$), lacking justification for inclusion of this variable in the model.

Turning to our hypotheses, the significant negative effect of perceived belief opposition in the *Moralistic model* and worsened model fit when restricting the effect of this variable to zero provide support for Hypothesis *H1a*: perceived belief opposition negatively affects social trust. On the other hand, the insignificant effect of normative expectations in *Rationalistic model* and the insignificant difference in model fit when restricting its effect to zero lead us to reject Hypothesis *H1b* that NE positively affect social trust. Direct comparison of both models' explained variance confirms that *Moralistic model* explains slightly more variance of social trust compared to *Rationalistic one*.

To check the assumption that negative and positive difference have a symmetric effect on social trust, we also ran the model with a binary variable reflecting the direction of the difference and its interaction with perceived belief opposition. The interaction turns out not to be significant in predicting social trust indicating that the effect of perceived belief opposition does not depend on the direction of that difference (online appendix Section 8).

We therefore proceed to test mediation within the *Moralistic model* where NE do not affect social trust. Testing if NE mediate the effect of EE on social trust as formulated within the rationalistic perspective is not needed, since we established that NE do not have an effect on social trust.

Table 4: Estimated parameters trust models

	<i>Moralistic</i>	<i>Rationalistic</i>
<i>Social trust (DV)</i>		
<i>NE</i>		0.012 (0.049)
<i>Perceived belief opposition</i> <i> PNB-NE </i>	-0.330*** (0.066)	

<i>Education</i>	0.011 (0.015)	0.011 (0.015)
<i>Risk attitude</i>	0.271*** (0.022)	0.274*** (0.023)
<i>Perceived economic threat</i>	-0.369*** (0.055)	-0.386*** (0.056)
<i>Age</i>	0.022*** (0.003)	0.022*** (0.003)
<i>Female</i>	-0.155+ (0.090)	-0.182* (0.090)
<i>Wave dummies</i>	yes	yes
<hr/>		
<i>Model fit</i>		
R^2	0.170	0.157
$R^2_{Adj.}$	0.164	0.150

*** $p < 0.001$ ** $p < 0.01$ * $p < 0.05$ + $p < 0.1$

Note: Robust standard errors of coefficients in parentheses. The end of the table with controls for survey waves is reported in the online appendix in Section 5.

Mediation hypotheses

In the second stage, models test whether the effect of perceived behaviour of others on social trust is mediated through perceived normative beliefs of others. Within the moralistic perspective, the effect of perceived behaviour opposition is mediated through perceived belief opposition, which were calculated as absolute differences between PNB and EE and NE, respectively. To check whether the prior transformation of EE to a 6-scale variable overestimated perceived behaviour opposition and thus, affected our mediation analysis, we also conducted our analysis with an alternative construction of perceived behaviour opposition. Our structural interpretation is robust since this analysis showed that the effect of alternatively constructed perceived behaviour opposition is also partially mediated by perceived belief opposition (online appendix Section 9).

In the *Main effect only model*, we first establish whether perceived behaviour opposition itself affects social trust (restricting the effect of the potential mediator, perceived belief opposition). Comparing the *Main effect only model* to its restricted version where the effect is not estimated shows that restricting the main effect of perceived behaviour opposition to zero significantly worsens the

model fit ($\Delta\chi^2(1) = 28.079, p < 0.001$), justifying the inclusion of the main effect of this variable in the model. From the *Main effect only model's* reasonable fit [$\chi^2(1, 1966) = 8.205, p = 0.004$; CFI = 0.980 (> 0.95); RMSEA = 0.061 ($\neq 0.05$); SRMR = 0.004 (< 0.08)] and the significance of the estimated main effect we can establish that the absolute difference between PNB and EE has a significant negative effect on social trust (Table 5): a unit increase in perceived behaviour opposition leads to 0.3 unit decrease in social trust ($b = -0.307, p < 0.001$).

The *Partial mediation* and *Full mediation model* add to the *Main effect only model* the mediation path, testing if perceived behaviour opposition affects social trust partially or fully through perceived belief opposition. The *Partial mediation model* shows that perceived behaviour opposition is a significant predictor of perceived belief opposition: a unit increase in behaviour opposition leads to 0.63 increase in perceived belief opposition. Hypothesis *H2* is therefore supported: the more a person perceives others act differently than what they themselves find socially appropriate ($|PNB-EE|$), the more likely they are to assume that others support different norms than those they themselves find socially appropriate ($|PNB-NE|$). Perceived behaviour opposition has a significant indirect ($b = -0.140, p = 0.01$) as well as direct effect ($b = -0.167, p = 0.048$) on social trust: a unit increase in perceived behaviour opposition leads to a 0.307 ($0.167 + 0.140$) unit decrease in social trust. Comparing the *Partial mediation model* to the *Full mediation model* shows that excluding the main effect of the perceived behaviour opposition significantly worsens the model fit ($\Delta\chi^2(1) = 4.911, p = 0.027$), justifying the inclusion of both a direct and indirect effect of perceived behaviour opposition. Hypothesis *H3* is therefore rejected: mediation is partial, not full.

Table 5: Estimated parameters of mediation models

	<i>Main effect only</i>	<i>Partial mediation</i>	<i>Full mediation</i>
<i>Social trust</i>			
$ PNB-EE $	-0.307*** (0.066)	-0.167* (0.085)	0
$ PNB-NE $	0	-0.220** (0.086)	-0.330*** (0.066)
<i>Education</i>	0.012 (0.015)	0.012 (0.015)	0.011 (0.015)

<i>Risk attitude</i>	0.270*** (0.022)	0.270*** (0.022)	0.271*** (0.022)
<i>Perceived economic threat</i>	-0.364*** (0.055)	-0.362*** (0.055)	-0.369*** (0.055)
<i>Age</i>	0.023*** (0.003)	0.023*** (0.003)	0.022*** (0.003)
<i>Female</i>	-0.154 ⁺ (0.090)	-0.149 ⁺ (0.090)	-0.155 ⁺ (0.090)
<i>Wave dummies</i>	yes	yes	yes
<i>Indirect effect</i>		-0.140** (0.054)	-0.209*** (0.044)
<hr/>			
<i>PNB-NE</i>			
<i>PNB-EE</i>		0.634*** (0.032)	0.634*** (0.032)
<i>Education</i>		0.001 (0.004)	0.001 (0.004)
<i>Risk attitude</i>		0.001 (0.006)	-0.001 (0.006)
<i>Perceived economic threat</i>		0.005 (0.015)	0.005 (0.015)
<i>Age</i>		-0.001 (0.001)	-0.001 (0.001)
<i>Female</i>		0.023 (0.025)	0.023 (0.025)
<i>Wave dummies</i>		yes	yes
<hr/>			
<i>Model fit</i>			
<i>R2 (Social trust)</i>	0.17	0.17	0.17
<i>R2 (PNB-NE)</i>		0.43	0.43
<i>χ²(df), p</i>	8.205(1), p = 0.004	0.000 (0)	4.911. (1), p = 0.027
<i>CFI</i>	0.980	1.000	0.997
<i>RMSEA</i>	0.061	0.000	0.045
<i>SRMR</i>	0.004	0.000	0.003

*** p < 0.001 **p < 0.01 * p < 0.05 ⁺p < 0.1

Note: Robust standard errors of coefficients in parentheses. The end of the table with controls for survey waves is reported in the online appendix in Section 6.

FIGURE 3. Final path model. Moralistic model with partial mediation of the effect of perceived behaviour difference.

5. Discussion and conclusion

The present paper studied how a person’s norm-related beliefs, PNB, NE and EE, affect social trust. By focussing on secondary beliefs as the main individual determinants of social trust, we were able to compare competing theoretical perspectives, moralistic and rationalistic, on social trust. The first explains social trust from the belief that others’ moral values align with one’s own (Uslaner, 2002). The second sees social trust as the consequence of the belief that others hold other-regarding preferences (Hardin, 2002).

In this study, we found support for the moralistic perspective and no support for the rationalistic perspective. A person’s perception that other people supported Covid-19 distancing norms (interpreted as willingness to incur individual costs of norm-compliance to contribute to a collective goal) did not positively influence their social trust. Rather, it was perceived similarity in Covid-19 norms support (and not support itself) that positively influenced social trust. Regarding the relationship between EE and NE, we found that if a person believes others behave differently than what they think is socially appropriate, they are more likely to believe others also hold different beliefs about which norms are socially appropriate. That people tend to evaluate others’ beliefs based on perceived behaviour of others

is a conclusion in line with other studies confirming interrelatedness of perceived norm compliance (EE) and perceived normative beliefs (NE) (Horne et al., 2018; Horne & Przepiorka, 2021).

Furthermore, we found that the perception that other people behave differently from what a person thinks is socially appropriate has a negative effect on their social trust, and that this effect is mediated through the perception of different beliefs of others. This sheds a light on studies focusing on how EE influence social trust (Lo Iacono et al., 2021; Wit & Lisciandra, 2021): in part, a person's perception of other's behaviour matters for social trust because they perceive it as an indicator of others' normative beliefs that have, in relation to their own normative beliefs, a significant effect on social trust. Perceived beliefs of others should therefore be accounted for when studying how perceived norm compliance affects social trust. However, others' opposing behaviour has a negative effect on social trust even when respondents do not translate it to others' opposing beliefs. This indicates that, contrary to our expectations, others' behaviour affects social trust also independently of serving as an indicator for others' beliefs.

So why does a person's perception that others behave differently to her values decrease social trust even when she does not translate this into others' "opposing" values? A possible explanation could be that "acting out of values" plays a role in social trust. If a person perceives others act differently to her moral values, but not because they would have different moral values themselves, she must assume others do not act out of their values as their values do not explain their actions. Perceived *integrity*, i.e., when someone's actions are perceived to result from their values, is an important element of perceived trustworthiness in psychological approaches (De George, 1993; Huberts, 2018). Consequently, if a person perceives others do not act according to their values, her social trust will be negatively affected by others' lack of integrity. In other words, every normative behaviour that is not attributable to a person's related normative beliefs, could be perceived as a sign of their untrustworthiness because their normative actions are not driven by their normative opinions regarding those actions but by other aims.

It should be noted that the support of the moralistic perspective in our empirical findings should be interpreted within the Italian Covid-19 context. Because managing the pandemic was a polarizing and politicized topic (Bertero & Seddone, 2021; Charron et al., 2023; Russo & Valbruzzi, 2022), the

differences between a person's own and perceived support for distancing norms might have had a heightened effect on social trust. Moreover, when translating rationalistic perspective into our hypotheses about how norm related beliefs affect social trust, we assumed that compliance to Covid-19 distancing norms represented expression of other-regarding preferences in the eyes of respondents, however this could be problematic. Namely, when consequences of people's actions are uncertain (as was the case for risks and benefits of (not) complying to distancing norms), people turn to other in-group members to interpret the social appropriateness of norm-prescribed behaviours (Horne & Johnson, 2021). Hence, it is precisely in times of crisis like the Covid-19 pandemic when consensus about the collective benefit of certain costly behaviours is difficult to establish (Vriens & Andrighetto, 2025). If some groups of respondents did not interpret norm adherence as theorized (i.e., as readiness to contribute to a societally beneficial goal), our operationalization does not test whether a person's social trust is founded upon perceived presence of other-regarding individuals in their society. The mismatch between our findings and those of Lo Iacono et al. (2021) presents a further reason to not discard the rationalistic theory yet. While we find no role of normative expectations on social trust in the context of the pandemic, they found that a person's perceptions that others support distancing norms decreased the loss of the person's social trust during the pandemic.

All in all, this study, in line with previous research, shows that secondary beliefs about values and behaviours of others are an important determinant for a person's social trust. However, to compare and test different theories of "origin" of social trust, accounts on how concretely these theories would be reflected in relationships between one's norm related beliefs must be further developed. How perceived value alignment with others influences social trust under conditions of perceived non-value-driven behaviour of others, for instance, is a question for future research. Additionally, although theories on social trust explain how norm-related beliefs affect social trust, it is possible that different individuals behave in line with different theories (Frederiksen, 2019). Future research on norm-related beliefs could therefore draw from research on other individual determinants of social trust, such as personality traits, optimism, egalitarianism, solidarity, and self-efficacy (Delhey & Newton, 2005; Frederiksen, 2019;

Uslaner, 2000, 2002), to determine whether different individuals have different constellations of norm-related beliefs that induce their social trust.

6. References

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